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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Infantile Marfan syndrome (MS) is a rare hereditary connective tissue disease with a poor prognosis. In this study, the clinical features and general prognosis of infantile MS cases were evaluated.

Materials and Methods: Four patients diagnosed with infantile MS between 2014 and 2024 were retrospectively analyzed. Two of the patients were male and two were female, and the median age at diagnosis was 6.5 months (range: 1-12 months). Presenting symptoms included murmur, chest deformity, and developmental delay.

Results: Skeletal findings were detected in all patients. Lens dislocation was detected in three patients. None of the cases had a family history. Cardiovascular examination revealed significant aortic root dilatation in all patients. In addition, mitral valve prolapse (MVP), mitral regurgitation (MR), and aortic regurgitation (AR) were observed in patients with aortic root dilatation. The median follow-up period of the cases was calculated as 33 months (range: 0-60 months). Valve-sparing aortic root replacement surgery was performed in one patient with significant aortic root dilatation, and permanent pacemaker implantation was performed due to complete atrioventricular block in the postoperative period. Valve-sparing surgery was indicated for another patient but was not accepted by the family. Another patient underwent valve-sparing surgery and mitral valve repair at the age of 18 months due to severe aortic root dilatation and MR, but the patient died in the postoperative period. Another patient was taken under clinical follow-up with the decision of the multidisciplinary council because of his young age. All cases were followed up with beta-blockers and angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors.

Conclusion: Infantile MS is a serious disease with high morbidity and mortality rates. Therefore, early diagnosis and timely intervention are critical to prevent possible complications.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Marfan syndrome, mitral valve prolapse, mitral regurgitation

INTRODUCTION

Marfan syndrome (MS) is a multisystemic connective tissue disorder with autosomal dominant inheritance. It is caused by mutations in the extracellular matrix protein fibrillin. Diagnostic findings include skeletal, ocular, cardiovascular, pulmonary, cutaneous and central nervous system abnormalities and family history (Judge & Dietz, 2005; Morse et al., 1990). The morphological features of the syndrome are age-related and phenotypic variability is remarkable. Most patients show de novo mutations (Morse et al., 1990). The term infantile Marfan syndrome is used to describe children with distinct phenotypic features at birth but with significant cardiovascular involvement in early infancy. Cardiovascular abnormalities are the primary cause of death in infantile MS and the most common findings are mitral and/or tricuspid valve insufficiency, which are less common in classical MS (Hennekam, 2005). The aim of this study is to evaluate the signs, symptoms, and

general prognosis of infantile MS cases diagnosed in a tertiary health institution in Turkey. It is also important since no such study was found in our country in the literature review.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Among 15 patients followed up with MS diagnosis between 2014-2024, four patients were diagnosed with infantile MS. MS diagnosis was based on the revised Gent criteria (Loeys et al., 2010). Gender, birth weight and height, age at diagnosis, follow-up period, other systemic involvements, family history, echocardiographic findings, gene testing, treatments, mortality information were recorded by retrospectively reviewing medical records. Data were presented with mean and standard deviation or median (minimum-maximum) according to the distribution of variables. The study was registered by Ordu University Clinical Research Ethics Committee (KA EK-339).

RESULTS

Two of the patients were male and two were female, and the median age at diagnosis was 6.5 months (range: 1-12 months). The median height at birth was 50 cm (range: 48-52 cm); however, during the growth process, the increase in height became apparent and exceeded the 75th percentile. The presenting symptoms included murmur, chest deformity, and developmental delay. The median follow-up period of the cases was calculated as 62.5 months (range: 6-120 months). The clinical characteristics of the patients are shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Clinical findings of the patients with infantile Marfan Syndrome

Case	Sex	At diagnosis age (mo)	Presenting symptom	Family history	Follow-up period (mo)
1	F	12	Murmur, chest deformity	Negative	120
2	M	12	Developmental delay, chest deformity	Negative	108
3	M	1	Murmur	Negative	18
4	F	1	Prenatal US (congenital knee dislocation)	Negative	6

US, ultrasonography

All cases had skeletal system findings (pectus carinatum, scoliosis, hyperelasticity, long extremities, arachnodactyly, tall stature). Lens dislocation was detected in three patients. None of the cases had a family history. Cardiovascular examination revealed significant aortic root dilatation in all patients. In addition, mitral valve prolapse (MVP), mitral regurgitation (MR), and aortic insufficiency (AR) were observed in patients with aortic root dilatation. Valve-sparing aortic root replacement surgery was performed in one patient with significant aortic root dilatation, and permanent pacemaker implantation was performed due to the development of complete atrioventricular block in the postoperative period. Valve-sparing surgery was indicated for another patient, but the family did not accept it. Another patient underwent valve-sparing surgery and mitral valve repair at the age of 18 months due to severe aortic root dilatation and MR, but the patient died in the postoperative period. Another patient was taken under clinical follow-up with the decision of the multidisciplinary council due to his young age (Table 2). All cases were followed up with beta-blockers and angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors.

Table 2

Cardiovascular and another system findings in patients with infantile Marfan Syndrome

Case	Aortic root ≥ 3	Echocardiogram findings	Skeletal findings	Ectopia lentis	FBN1 gene mutation	Mortality
1	84 mm (8)	MVP, MR	Pectus carinatum, scoliosis	+	+	Alive
2	42 mm (6.1)	MVP, MR	Pectus carinatum, scoliosis, hyperelasticity	+	+	Alive
3	35 mm (8)	MVP, MR, AR	Pectus carinatum, arachnodactyly, long limbs, tall stature	+	+	Dead
4	19 mm (4.6)	AR	Arachnodactyly	NA	+	Alive

MVP, mitral valve prolapse; MR, mitral regurgitation; AR, aortic regurgitation; NA, not available

DISCUSSION

MS, a systemic disease of the connective tissue, is seen in approximately 1-2 out of 10,000 people. However, it is difficult to determine the true incidence because the symptoms of the disease become more pronounced with age (Judge & Dietz, 2005). The first diagnostic criteria were determined in 1988, and today the diagnosis is based on skeletal, ocular, cardiovascular, skin, central nervous system and pulmonary system features in addition to family history and FBN1 mutations (Loeys et al., 2010). Infantile MS is a rarely diagnosed MS type with atypical and severe effects on the cardiovascular system (Das et al., 2015). In classical MS, the cardiovascular events leading to death are mostly aortic dissection or rupture; however, deaths in infantile MS patients are related to CHF due to MR or TR (Pyeritz & Wappel, 1983). Three of our patients had MR detected in their ECHO, accompanied by MVP and AR.

It is known that the prognosis of infantile MS diagnosed in the first year of life is poor. It is reported that the life expectancy of infantile MS patients is less than 2 years due to the severity of cardiovascular problems (Shih, Liu, & Chen, 2004). One of our four patients died at the age of 18 months. Infantile MS is generally thought to be caused by a new mutation rather than a positive family history (Shih, Liu, & Chen, 2004). None of our patients had a family history, and all were FBN1 mutation positive. The majority of patients require both medical and surgical treatment to prevent cardiovascular complications. In pediatric MS patients, the use of beta blockers is recommended because it delays cardiac interventions (Keane & Pyeritz, 2008). However, the benefits of beta blocker use in infantile MS are not fully known (Buchhorn et al., 2014; Morse et al., 1990). All of our patients were also using beta blockers. Despite multiple drug use, valve surgery is usually necessary because MR triggers congestive heart failure and can lead to sudden cardiac death (Keane & Pyeritz, 2008). However, conditions such as complete heart block, thrombosis, and stroke may occur after valve surgery (Kim et al., 2015). In our patients who underwent valve-sparing aortic root replacement surgery, one developed complete block after the operation, and the other died after surgery.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is very important to recognize infantile MS immediately after birth to perform diagnostic studies and initiate appropriate treatment in time.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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